

ON LOAD DISTRIBUTION FACTORS IN RADIALY LOADED ROLLING ELEMENT BEARINGS†

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Abstract. A rolling element bearing is a device generally consisting of two concentric steel rings, where two grooves are machined: an inner groove is machined in the outer ring and an outer groove is machined in the inner ring. Rolling elements are placed between the grooves: cylindrical, conical and spherical rollers or balls. A rolling bearing provides load transmission between two structures, generally called shaft and housing, maintaining the relative position between the structures, but allowing one or two rotational and/or translational degrees of freedom. The external load of the bearing is transferred from one ring to the other through the rolling elements, and the device's stiffness, performance and life depend on the load distribution across the rolling elements, which is not uniform. The load distribution depends on the rings and rolling elements' materials, the internal geometry of the bearing and the magnitude and direction of the external load. An internal parameter that has a strong influence is the radial clearance. Mitrović, Lazović et al., obtained load distribution factors for ball bearings subjected to external radial load, with positive and zero radial clearances, which are a measure of the rolling elements participation in the external radial load distribution. However, the factors defined by them are not suitable for bearings with negative radial clearance (interference), since they are based on the calculation of rolling elements that participate in the transfer of external radial load, which is only valid for zero and positive radial clearance. Here the load distribution factors are obtained for ball and cylindrical roller bearings with positive, negative and zero radial clearances. A total of 42 figures is shown in this work, many of which are made up of sub-figures. A total of 198 figures and sub-figures is shown.

Keywords: radial clearance, load distribution factor, radial load

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1. INTRODUCTION

Many machines and mechanical devices have shafts supported by rolling element bearings. A rolling element bearing is a device generally consisting of two concentric steel rings, where two grooves are machined: an inner groove is machined in the outer ring and an outer groove is machined in the inner ring. Rolling elements are placed between the grooves: cylindrical, conical or spherical rollers, or balls. A rolling element bearing provides load transmission between two structures, generally a shaft and housing, maintaining the relative position between the structures, but allowing 1 or 2 rotational and/or translational degrees of freedom. The stiffness of the shaft in relation to the housing, as well as the device's performance, load capacity, vibration levels and life are strongly influenced by internal rolling element bearing's parameters, materials and external loads. The external load of the bearing is transferred from one ring to the other through the rolling elements, and the stiffness depends on the load's distribution across the rolling elements, which is not uniform. The load distribution depends on the internal geometry of the bearing and the magnitude and direction of the external load. An internal parameter, which has a strong influence, is the radial clearance.

Stribeck [1] was the pioneer to investigate the distribution of loads on the rolling elements of a radially loaded ball bearing and found that the *maximum* ball load could be derived by multiplying the *average* load by 4.37, for zero internal clearance. This result is an approximation of the value found when considering an infinite number of balls, of infinitesimal diameter, symmetrically and evenly distributed in relation to the load line, which passes through the most loaded ball's center. This number came to be known as Stribeck's Number or Constant and, to account for nonzero diametrical clearance and other effects, Stribeck recommended rounding the Constant to 5.0.

Palmgren [2] stated that the theoretical value of Stribeck's Constant for roller bearings with zero internal clearance is 4.08 and suggested using Stribeck's recommended value of 5.0 for the Stribeck's Constant for either ball or roller bearings having typical clearance.

Ricci [3] showed how the Stribeck's Constants were found. It's also shown that the error when adopting the value 4.08 for roller bearing Stribeck's Constant is 55.6 times greater than when adopting the value 4.37 for the ball bearing Stribeck's Constant.

Sjövall [4] proposed an integral method for load distribution calculation in bearings. The relationship between the load on the most loaded rolling element and the bearing loading was established using Sjövall's integrals. Houpert [5] improved Sjövall's integrals for multi-degree-of-freedom bearing system. A comprehensive mathematical model of bearings was developed by Harris [6]. The load zone was described by the load distribution factor, ϵ , and the contact stress-strain relationship between the ring and any rolling element was achieved. The load distribution can be obtained by continuous iteration procedure. However, studies have shown [7, 8] that the results obtained by the Harris method cannot rigorously satisfy the static balance. Pointing out that the problem of obtaining the load distribution in bearings with arbitrary radial clearance is to determine the number of rolling elements that participate in the transfer of the external radial load. Tomović [7, 8] considers two boundary positions of support of the inner ring and proposed a simple method to determine the number of rolling elements in the loading zone.

Considering two different distributions of the balls in relation to the load line, Sinha and Sahoo [9] obtained a better load distribution in ball bearings under the influence of the relative motion between the rings in the presence of radial clearance.

Ball bearing clearance influences starting torque, bearing stiffness and affects load distribution, load carrying capacity and bearing life. Sinha *et al.* [10] calculated the radial load distribution in a deep groove ball bearing with variable clearance - which is obtained by constructing the outer ring's groove in an elliptical shape - and the results shown that the load distribution is better when compared to the conventional bearing, for $|\theta| < \pi/4$, where θ is the angle between the load line and the major axis of the elliptical outer groove.

Using the Lundberg and Palmgren model and the finite element method, Chudzik and Warda [11] determined the stress distributions needed to estimate the fatigue life of a radial cylindrical roller bearing under the influence of radial internal clearance. The result reveals that the radial cylindrical roller bearing will have higher fatigue strength with a slight radial clearance.

The changes of rolling element position may cause continuous change of radial stiffness and relative displacement of inner and outer ring during the operation of the bearing-rotor systems. In order to accurately study the influence of the changes of rolling element position on radial stiffness, Han *et al.* [12] proposed a mathematical method for rolling bearings modeling and stiffness calculation based on Hertz elastic contact theory, where two boundary positions of the inner ring supported by even or odd number of rolling elements are considered. The effect of bearing parameters including internal clearance and number of rolling elements on the fluctuation of radial stiffness and oscillation of rotor's center has been systematically investigated for ball and roller bearings.

Zhang *et al.* [13] proposed a model to study the load distribution in a ball bearing as a preload's function. Preload means negative radial internal clearance. The new model is then used to calculate fatigue life as a function of external load, rotational speed and preload. The results show that adequate preload improves load distribution and prolongs fatigue life. Given load and rotational speed, an optimal preload can be obtained, estimated through the life of the bearing.

Research has shown that ball bearings should have slightly negative or zero internal clearance to maximize bearing life and reliability. However, zero or slightly negative clearance generates high contact stresses between raceways and balls [14, 15]. In addition, it increases bearing friction, which makes the bearing vulnerable to temperature rise. Therefore, a bearing with positive radial clearance is generally chosen to avoid such problems [9].

Xiaoli *et al.* [14] developed a mathematical model based on the Hertz elastic contact theory to determine the radial load distribution in ball bearings with positive, negative and zero clearance. Oswald *et al.* [15] investigated the effect of internal clearance on load distribution and fatigue life of radially loaded deep groove ball bearings. They found that life gradually decreases with increasing radial clearance's absolute value and is maximum under small negative radial clearance. Furthermore, in radially loaded bearings, the rolling elements, which transfer the load - active elements -, for zero radial clearance, are located below the meridian plane in the so-called *loading zone*. The quasi-static analysis to derive the radial load distribution is based on the assumption that the rigid inner ring, under load, moves radially in the direction of the external load, with respect to the rigid outer ring.

Ricci [16, 17] has developed numerical procedures whose analogues haven't been found in the literature. The equilibrium solutions for internal load distribution in single row, statically loaded angular contact ball bearings subject to known radial, axial and

combined moment's loads, are derived using the Newton-Raphson method. The procedure has been used to find load distribution differences between a loaded, unfitted bearing at room temperature and the same bearing loaded with interference fits, which can experience radial temperature gradients between the inner and outer rings. For each step of the procedure, the iterative solution of $z + 2$ simultaneous algebraic nonlinear equations is required - where z is the number of balls - to produce an exact solution for the axial and radial deflections and the contact angles.

Ricci [18] observed that there are two basic methods for radial external load distribution computation on rolling elements in a rolling element bearing: the discrete method and the integral method. According to him, solving the discrete equilibrium quasi-static equation using the Newton-Raphson scheme, more accurate results are derived than those based on the integral method, with small theoretical and computational efforts. The Sjövall's radial integral factors, as well as some approximations proposed in the literature, for line- and point-contacts, were revisited. Numerical approximations for the Sjövall's radial integrals were proposed. The approximations' errors with respect to the Sjövall's radial integral's numerical integration were shown. The numerical results of the displacement between inner and outer rigid rings, maximum hertzian contact deflection and the most loaded element load were shown for some ball and roller bearings, for radial external load ranging from 0 to 10,000 N, and for positive, negative and zero radial clearance, solving the discrete equilibrium quasi-static equation using the Newton-Raphson method.

Mitrović [19] carried out an analytical study of the influence of radial internal clearance on the static load rating of bearings. To analyze the influence, a parameter was introduced: the load distribution factor, which is the ratio between the load on the most loaded ball and the external radial load. The ratio introduced in Eq. (3) of the Mitrović's paper is a function of the rolling elements' azimuth angles and the *relative radial clearance parameter with respect to the total relative displacement between rings*, $P_d/(2\delta)$, and measures the participation of the most loaded rolling element in the external radial load distribution. Lazović *et al.* [20] generalized the notion of load distribution factor introducing a slightly different load distribution factor, which is the ratio between the rolling element's load component in the radial external load direction and the external radial load. They also introduced the definition of the *reduced* load distribution factor, which is the ratio between the rolling element's load and the external radial load. The ratios that appear in Eqs. (13) and (16) of the Lazović *et al.*'s paper are functions of the rolling elements' azimuth angles and the *relative radial clearance parameter with respect to the elastic compression in the load line*, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. They provided an overview of the load distribution of ball bearings with zero and positive radial clearance. However, as we will see, the load distribution factors, as defined by both Mitrović and Lazović *et al.*, aren't suitable for bearings, which have some negative radial clearance. This is because the models don't allow negative radial clearance and also both use a parameter named z_s to define the load distribution factors, which represents the active rolling elements number, which transfer the external radial load. However, such a parameter as defined is only valid for bearings, which have zero radial clearance.

The unevenness of the load distribution increases with the radial internal clearance. Kostić *et al.* [22] used an analytical and numerical approach to determine the load transmitted by the rolling elements.

There are in the literature two definitions for *load distribution factor* with respect radially loaded rolling element bearings. One of them assumes that the load distribution

can be given by a radial integral and the load distribution factor, ε , is defined as being the ratio between the load zone projected on the load line and the diameter [4, 5]. The second assumes that the load distribution satisfies the static equilibrium equation given by a sum of the discrete rolling elements' loads components in the radial external load direction. In this case, the load distribution factor is defined as the ratio between the rolling element's load component in the radial external load direction and the external radial load [19, 20].

In this work, the rolling elements' load distribution factors of a radially loaded rolling element bearing are derived in the same way as was done by Lazović *et al.* [20] for ball bearings. However, unlike Lazović *et al.*, here I address load distribution factors not only as functions of the relative radial clearance parameter with respect to elastic compression at the load line, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, but also as functions of the relative radial clearance parameter with respect to the total relative displacement between the rings, $P_d/(2\delta)$. Here the radial clearance *sign* is also considered, and load distribution factors are also obtained for cylindrical roller bearings. Since the mechanical system can operate with positive, negative or null clearances, I presume that the introduction of the radial clearance sign in rolling element bearing models is a measure that makes them improved. Recently, it has been discovered that increased life and performance without noise and vibrations is related to a small negative radial clearance, or preload [15]. Generally, a small positive clearance is used to avoid the effects of radial temperature gradients, which can even lock the shaft's motion with respect to the housing.

The first section of this work presents an introduction on the subject. In the second section, the formula for the j^{th} rolling element's clearance, c_j , $j = 1, \dots, z$, is derived, which is a function of the radial clearance, $P_d/2$, which can be positive, negative, or zero, and the j^{th} rolling element's azimuth angle, ψ_j . The formula for the j^{th} rolling element's elastic compression, δ_j , as a function of j^{th} rolling element's clearance and azimuth angle, and the further elastic compression, δ_{\max} , on the rolling element most loaded, is also obtained. One figure is shown in section 2. In the third section an inspection is made on the ratio between the most loaded rolling element's load and the external radial load, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, as a function of the two relative radial clearances, $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, and the bearing rolling elements number, z . This section features 20 figures (96 sub-figures). The fourth section addresses the ratio between the j^{th} rolling element's load and the external radial load, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, as a function of the relative radial clearances and bearing's rolling elements number. This section contains 21 figures (101 sub-figures). Finally, the paper's conclusions, acknowledgments and bibliographical references addressed in the text are presented.

2. ELASTIC COMPRESSION OF ROLLING ELEMENTS IN RADIALLY LOADED BEARINGS

Let a single row ball or cylindrical roller bearing with rigid rings and z rolling elements symmetrically distributed with respect to the radial load line and evenly spaced about a pitch circle to be subjected to a radial load. Then, a *relative radial displacement*, δ , of the inner ring with respect to the outer ring may be expected. Let's consider that the load line passes through the *most* loaded rolling element's center. Let ψ the azimuth angle measured from the load line (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Rolling elements azimuth angular positions in the radial plane, which is perpendicular to the bearing's axis of rotation, $\Delta\psi = 2\pi/z$, $\psi_j = \Delta\psi(j-1)$, $j = 1, \dots, z$; P_d is the radial clearance; D is the rolling element diameter; d_i and d_o are inner and outer raceways diameters, respectively

Radial bearings are generally designed to have a *radial clearance*, P_d . The original radial clearance, as a result of the bearing manufacturing process, can change after fitting the bearing to the shaft and housing, and in operation when subjected to radial temperature gradients; and even can result in interference (preloading). Therefore, in this work, radial clearance is considered to be the *operational radial clearance*, which is the result of the manufacturing, assembly and operation process - disregarding the application of external load - and not the original radial clearance arising from the manufacturing process only. Assuming that the bearing operates on a stationary radial thermal gradient between the rings, then the operating radial clearance can be thought as a positive, negative or zero *constant*.

In a radially loaded bearing, with *positive* radial clearance, $P_d > 0$, the diameter $d_o - 2D$ is greater than d_i , where D is the rolling element's diameter; d_i and d_o are inner and outer raceways diameters, respectively. If the inner ring is concentric with the outer ring, a uniform radial clearance of $P_d/2$, of the inner ring with respect the outer ring, is observed. Under load, if the load line passes through the center of the most loaded rolling element, i.e., the rolling element located in $\psi = \psi_j = 0^\circ$, $j = 1$, the application of a small radial load to the shaft causes the inner ring to move a distance $P_d/2$ in relation to the outer ring, before contact between the rolling element located on the load line and the inner and outer raceways [21].

If the radial clearance is *negative*, i.e., $P_d < 0$, the diameter d_i is greater than $d_o - 2D$, and, in an unloaded bearing, there is a uniform radial *interference* of $|P_d|/2$, of the inner ring with respect the outer ring. The application of an *initial* radial load to the shaft causes the inner ring to move a distance $|P_d|/2$ with respect to the outer ring, before the *least* loaded rolling element located in $\psi = \psi_j = 180^\circ$, $j = (z + 2)/2$, if z is even, is released from the inner and outer raceways.

The objective of this section is to obtain a simple formula for the elastic deflection $\delta_j \triangleq \delta(\psi_j)$ as a function of the relative displacement between the rings, δ , in the presence of radial clearance, $P_d/2$; which can be positive, negative or zero. If the radial

clearance is zero the displacement δ is equal to the deflection in the most loaded rolling element, δ_{\max} , and the elastic deflection can be approximated by $\delta_j \approx \delta \cos \psi_j$ [1]. If the radial clearance is positive, the displacement δ is equal to the hertzian deflection in the most loaded rolling element, δ_{\max} , added to the radial clearance, $P_d/2$. But, if radial clearance is negative, the total hertzian deflection of the most loaded rolling element is δ_{\max} plus the absolute value of the radial clearance, P_d . This is why δ_{\max} is called further deflection. To obtain δ_j one must subtract the *clearance*, $c_j \triangleq c(\psi_j)$, from the formula presented by Stribeck [1].

The literature has shown formulas for the clearance as a function of the azimuth angle and the radial clearance [6, 20, 21], but few researchers take account the radial clearance's sign. Xiaoli *et al.* [14] considers pre-deformation to be a negative radial clearance, but there is much to be explored on the subject. Therefore, in this work, the radial clearance or interference, c_j , at a given azimuth angle ψ_j , if $|P_d|$ is small compared to the radius of the tracks, can be expressed with adequate precision by

$$c_j = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{|P_d|}{P_d} \cos \psi_j\right) \frac{P_d}{2} & \text{if } P_d \neq 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } P_d = 0. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

If $P_d > 0$, on the load line where $\psi_j = 0^\circ$, the clearance is zero; and where $\psi_j = 180^\circ$ the clearance is P_d . If $P_d < 0$ the clearance is zero at $\psi_j = 180^\circ$ and P_d (interference) at $\psi_j = 0^\circ$.

The application of further load will cause elastic deformation of the rolling elements and elimination of clearance along a $2\psi_l$ arc. If the further elastic interference or compression in the load line is δ_{\max} the corresponding elastic compression δ_j of the rolling elements along a radius at an angle ψ_j to the load line is given by

$$\delta_j = \delta_{\max} \cos \psi_j - c_j, \quad (2)$$

which assumes that the rings are rigid.

Substituting (1) in (2), yields

$$\delta_j = \delta \cos \psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\delta \triangleq \delta_{\max} + \frac{|P_d|}{2} \quad (4)$$

represents the *total relative radial displacement* between inner and outer rings.

3. RATIOS BETWEEN RADIAL EXTERNAL LOAD AND MAXIMUM ROLLING ELEMENT'S LOAD

If P is a radial external load, assuming the rolling elements distribution shown in Fig. 1, yields

$$P = \sum_{j=1}^z P_j \cos \psi_j, \quad (5)$$

where P_j , $j = 1, \dots, z$, are rolling elements' normal loads for rolling elements located at the azimuth angles ψ_j , with the portions of the sum referring to rolling elements, which don't participate in the load transfer, being assumed to be null.

Assuming that

$$P_j = k_n \delta_j^n, \quad j = 1, \dots, z, \quad (6)$$

where k_n is a load-deflection proportionality constant, $n = 3/2$ for ball bearings [1] and $n = 10/9$ for cylindrical roller bearings [2], then, dividing P_1 by Eq. (5), yields

$$\frac{P_1}{P} = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n}{\sum_{j=1}^z \left(\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_j} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}} - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)^n}{\sum_{j=1}^z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right) \cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_j}, \quad (7)$$

which is a function of the rolling elements' azimuth angles and the *relative* radial clearance parameter. There are two relative radial clearance parameters. One of them is with respect to the total relative displacement between rings, δ , and the other is with respect to the further elastic interference or compression in the load line, δ_{\max} .

The ratio between the maximum rolling element's load, P_1 , and the radial external load, P , given by Eq. (7), for $n = 3/2$, as a function of total relative displacement between rings, δ , is the definition of the Mitrović's load distribution factor [19]. However, the Eq. (7), with δ given by Eq. (4) and P_d positive, negative or zero, yields a more generic result than the Mitrović's results, since here I assume that P_1/P isn't only a radial clearance function, but also a radial clearance's *sign* function. Furthermore, here the load distribution factor is defined not only for ball bearings, but also for cylindrical roller bearings. Another fact to be highlighted and which has already been mentioned here is that the Mitrović's model for the load distribution factor isn't appropriate if the radial clearance is negative. To determine the external load in the denominator of the factor, the quasi-static force balance discrete equation in the external radial load direction is used, which is the sum of the loads on the active rolling elements. However, as we will see, the Mitrović's way to obtain the active elements number is only valid for bearings with zero or positive radial clearance.

Figure 2 shows the excerpt taken from Stribeck's paper [1], where he comes to the conclusion that the constant, which must be multiplied by the average load to obtain the maximum ball load, in a radially loaded ball bearing with zero radial clearance, is 4.37. The values circled by the red ellipses were derived by Stribeck from the $P/P_1 - P/P_0$ in the Fig. 2 – ratio for bearings with 10, 15 and 20 balls.

From which calculation we have for instance for

$z =$	10	15	20
$\gamma =$	36°	24°	18°
$\frac{P}{P_o}$	2.28	3.44	4.58
$=$	$\frac{z}{4.38}$	$\frac{z}{4.36}$	$\frac{z}{4.37}$

$$P_o + 2P_1 + \dots + 2P_n = 1.23 P \quad 1.22 P \quad 1.21 P$$

S9 The sum of the individual loads is almost invariable and the

values also of $\frac{P}{P_o}$ are almost exactly equal to $\frac{z}{4.37}$.

Fig. 2 – Excerpt taken from Stribeck's paper
Source: Stribeck [1], p. 452

Figures (3) to (21), below, show loads ratios plots involving the external radial load P and the most loaded rolling element load, P_1 . Plots of the effective number of rolling elements are also shown, i.e., active rolling elements, which effectively work on transferring the external radial load. Plots and figures are given as functions of the *relative* radial clearances, $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$, and the total number z of rolling elements in the bearing. In these plots, z generally ranges from 2 to 20 and for some ratios plots the blue line is for ball bearing and the red line is for cylindrical roller bearing.

3.1. P_1/P ratios plots

Figures 3(a) to (f) show P_1/P ratios plots, i.e., plots of Eq. (7), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$ values, as z 's functions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 3 – P_1/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); for some $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f) - values adopted by Stribeck [1] for 10, 15 and 20 balls, circled by the red ellipses in Fig. 2, also are shown

Figures 3(a) to (c) show that, for a relative radial clearance $P_d/(2\delta) = 0.5$, if the bearing has up to 6 rolling elements, the most loaded rolling element transfers all the external load. The same occurs for a relative radial clearance $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 2.5$ and if the bearing has up to 8 rolling elements, as shown in the Figs. 3(d) to (f). Note that for relative radial clearance $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -2.5$ and bearing with 3 rolling elements, $P_1 > P$, indicating that the most loaded rolling element is transferring a load greater than the external radial load.

According to Figure 3, the participation of the most loaded rolling element in transferring the external radial load decreases with the increase of rolling elements in the bearing, whatever the relative radial clearance. Numerical results confirm the statement made by Lazović *et al.* [20] for the ideal case of ball bearing with zero radial clearance and equal distribution of external radial load that, with the increase in the number of rolling elements in the bearing, the participation of the most loaded rolling

element in the transfer of external radial load tends to the reciprocal of the active rolling elements number. However, this was observed not only for the case of zero radial clearance and equal distribution of the external radial load, but also for whatever relative radial clearance and actual distribution. Figs. 3(b), (c), (e) and (f) clearly show that the P_1/P ratios, for any value of relative radial clearances, tend, as the number of rolling elements in the bearing increases, towards a dashed horizontal line representing the reciprocal of the active number of rolling elements for $P_d/(2\delta) = P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 0$ and $z = 20$, z being chosen here as the highest value in the graph range. Other ranges for z were tested and the same behavior was noticed. Fig. 4 shows the P_1/P ratios, for some values of the relative radial clearances and an extremely high range of consecutive twenty z values.

(c)

(d)

Fig. 4 – P_1/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings and an extremely high range of consecutive twenty z values as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) and (b); as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) and (d)

The increase in the value of z must be accompanied by an adequate reduction in the diameter of the rolling element, so that they can all fit properly within the bearing circumference. For all relative radial clearance values shown in Fig 4 there is a slight decrease in the P_1/P ratios, with the increase in z , which is not noticeable in the plots. Dashed lines representing the reciprocals of the active rolling element numbers for the adopted values of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ are also shown.

Figures 5(a) to (f) show P_1/P ratios plots, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions.

Fig. 5 – P_1/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings and some z values as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) to (c); as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (d) to (f)

According to Figs. 5(a) and (d), given two bearings, a ball bearing and a cylindrical roller bearing, with the same number of rolling elements, the P_1/P ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller (ball) bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball (cylindrical roller) bearing if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the second (fourth) columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The P_1/P ratio values computed for both ball and roller bearings are equal to 1, if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the sixth columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The numerous dashed vertical lines that appear in the figures, which are functions of the relative radial clearance parameters, indicate the parameters values at which there is a decrease, for the next odd number, in the active rolling elements number when the parameter increases, to *some* z rolling elements value.

Tab. 1 - P_1/P^1 ratio values for ball and roller bearings and some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions

z	$P_d/(2\delta)$	P_1/P^1	$P_d/(2\delta)$	P_1/P^1	$P_d/(2\delta)$	P_1/P^1	
2	$(-\infty, -1)$	$[P_1/P]_{\text{roller}} >^2 [P_1/P]_{\text{ball}}$	-	-	$(-1, +1)$	$[P_1/P]_{\text{roller}} = [P_1/P]_{\text{ball}} = 1^3$	
3	$(-\infty, -0.5)$				$(-0.5, +1)$		
4	$(-\infty, -1)$				$(-1, +1)$		
5	$(-\infty, -0.960)$				$(-0.960, +0.309)$		$(0.309, +1)$
6	$(-\infty, -0.895)$				$(-0.895, +0.5)$		$(0.5, +1)$
7	$(-\infty, -0.967)$				$(-0.967, +0.623)$		$(0.623, +1)$
8	$(-\infty, -0.930)$				$(-0.930, +0.707)$		$(0.707, +1)$
9	$(-\infty, -0.968)$				$(-0.968, +0.766)$		$(0.766, +1)$
10	$(-\infty, -0.943)$				$(-0.943, +0.809)$		$(0.809, +1)$
11	$(-\infty, -0.967)$				$(-0.967, +0.841)$		$(0.841, +1)$
12	$(-\infty, -0.949)$				$(-0.949, +0.866)$		$(0.866, +1)$
13	$(-\infty, -0.960)$				$(-0.960, +0.885)$		$(0.885, +1)$
14	$(-\infty, -0.953)$				$(-0.953, +0.901)$		$(0.901, +1)$
15	$(-\infty, -0.954)$				$(-0.954, +0.914)$		$(0.914, +1)$
16	$(-\infty, -0.956)$				$(-0.956, +0.924)$		$(0.924, +1)$
17	$(-\infty, -0.952)$				$(-0.952, +0.932)$		$(0.932, +1)$
18	$(-\infty, -0.957)$				$(-0.957, +0.940)$		$(0.940, +1)$
19	$(-\infty, -0.952)$				$(-0.952, +0.946)$		$(0.946, +1)$
20	$(-\infty, -0.958)$				$(-0.958, +0.951)$		$(0.951, +1)$

Tab. 2 - P_1/P^1 ratio values for ball and roller bearings and some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions

z	$P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$	P_1/P^1	$P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$	P_1/P^1	$P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$	P_1/P^1
2	-	$[P_1/P]_{\text{roller}} >^2 [P_1/P]_{\text{ball}}$	-	-	$(-\infty, +20)$	$[P_1/P]_{\text{roller}} = [P_1/P]_{\text{ball}} = 1^3$
3	$(-\infty, -1)$				$(-1, +20)$	
4	-				$(-\infty, +20)$	

¹ Tab. 1 and Tab. 2 with minor modifications are also valid for P/P_1 , zP_1/P and $P/(zP_1)$. Therefore, where P_1/P is read, read P/P_1 , zP_1/P or $P/(zP_1)$, as the case may be.

² change math symbols $>$ to $<$ and vice versa for P/P_1 and $P/(zP_1)$.

³ replace the last column with z for zP_1/P and with z^{-1} for $P/(zP_1)$.

5	($-\infty, -24.281$)	(-24.281,+0.45)	$\frac{[P_1/P]_{\text{roller}}}{[P_1/P]_{\text{ball}}} < 2$	(0.45,+20)
6	($-\infty, -8.496$)	(-8.496,+1)		(1,+20)
7	($-\infty, -29.530$)	(-29.530,+1.66)		(1.66,+20)
8	($-\infty, -13.313$)	(-13.313,+2.42)		(2.42,+20)
9	($-\infty, -29.816$)	(-29.816,+3.28)		(3.28,+20)
10	($-\infty, -16.543$)	(-16.543,+4.24)		(4.24,+20)
11	($-\infty, -29.461$)	(-29.461,+5.3)		(5.3,+20)
12	($-\infty, -18.754$)	(-18.754,+6.47)		(6.47,+20)
13	($-\infty, -23.959$)	(-23.959,+7.74)		(7.74,+20)
14	($-\infty, -20.324$)	(-20.324,+9.10)		(9.10,+20)
15	($-\infty, -20.541$)	(-20.541,+10.57)		(10.57,+20)
16	($-\infty, -21.475$)	(-21.475,+12.14)		(12.14,+20)
17	($-\infty, -19.884$)	(-19.884,+13.81)		(13.81,+20)
18	($-\infty, -22.334$)	(-22.334,+15.59)		(15.59,+20)
19	($-\infty, -19.952$)	(-19.952,+17.46)		(17.46,+20)
20	($-\infty, -22.969$)	(-22.969,+19.44)		(19.44,+20)

As can be seen from Fig. 5, if $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ increases, the P_1/P ratio values tend towards 1 and reach the value 1 sooner or later, depending on the number of rolling elements in the bearing. The greater the numbers of rolling elements in the bearing, the later P_1/P ratio values reach the value 1. Note that the $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter never reaches or exceeds the value 1, regardless of the number of rolling elements in the bearing. If this happened, it would mean that the relative displacement between the rings would be less than or equal to the radial clearance and, therefore, there would be no rolling element/race contact on any of the rolling elements. Unlike what it's observed for the $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter, there is no theoretical superior boundary for the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter. Each rolling element added to the bearing expands the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ range, in which P_1/P is less than 1. Note also that with increasing $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, when the P_1/P ratio reaches the value 1, it is reached for both ball and roller bearings with the same number of rolling elements, for a single $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ value.

If $P_d/(2\delta) < -0.5$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) < -1$ and $z = 3$, or $P_d/(2\delta) < -1$ and $z = 2$ or 4 , the P_1/P ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball bearing and in both cases, $P_1/P > 1$. This means that, for these $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges, and for these numbers of rolling elements in the bearing, the most loaded rolling element load is greater than the external radial load. Besides, for the same z value, the most loaded cylindrical roller transfers a greater portion of the external radial load than the most loaded ball. This is due to the fact that radial clearance is negative in these ranges; therefore, all rolling elements are under preload before the external radial load is applied. With the application of the external radial load, two rolling elements are released when $P_d = -\delta = -2\delta_{\max}$, $\delta, \delta_{\max} > 0$ for the bearing with three rolling elements. For the bearing with two or four rolling elements the release of the rolling element, which is located at $\psi = 180^\circ$, occurs when $P_d = -2\delta$. Note that two rolling elements of the bearing with four rolling elements never participate in the transfer of the external radial load. Therefore, for $z = 2$ and 4 the P_1/P ratio values are equal. If $P_d/(2\delta) \geq -0.5$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) \geq -1$ and $z = 3$, or $P_d/(2\delta) \geq -1$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ any, and $z = 2$ or 4 , $P_1/P = 1$ for both bearings, indicating that, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ increases from these values, all the external radial load is being transferred by a single rolling element, i.e., the rolling element number 1, according to Fig. 1.

The P_1/P ratio values computed for the ball bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing, if $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ is greater than a value, which can be between -29.5 up to -8.5 , depending on the number of rolling elements in the bearing, at least if the number of rolling elements is greater than or equal to 5, as can be seen from Figs. 3(d) and 5(d). Unlike what it's observed for the P_1/P ratio values as a $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter function, the P_1/P ratio values as a $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter function vary little - it is almost a plateau, denoted more for ball bearings than roller bearings - for negative values of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter and for any number of rolling elements in the bearing. For a given $z \geq 5$, increasing the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter from zero causes the P_1/P ratio values to increase, from the characteristic plateau, for the given number of rolling elements, to the value 1.

Figures 6(a) to (d) show 3D-plots of the P_1/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20.

Fig. 6 – P_1/P ratios. As z and $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) ball bearings, (b) cylindrical roller bearings. As z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) ball bearings, (d) cylindrical roller bearings

3.2. P/P_1 ratios plots

Figures 7(a) to (f) show P/P_1 ratios plots, i.e., plots of the reciprocal of Eq. (7), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, as z 's functions.

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 7 – P/P_1 ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); for some $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f) - values adopted by Stribeck [1] for 10 and 15 balls, circled by the red ellipses in Fig. 2, also are shown

Figures 8(a) to (f) show P/P_1 ratios plots, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig. 8 – P/P_1 ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings and some z values as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) to (c); as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (d) to (f)

According to Figs. 8(a) and (d), given two bearings, a ball bearing and a cylindrical roller bearing, with the same number of rolling elements, the P/P_1 ratio values computed for the ball (cylindrical roller) bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller (ball) bearing for the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges given, as z functions, in the second (fourth) columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The P/P_1 ratio values computed for both ball and roller bearings are equal to 1, if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the sixth columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

The P/P_1 ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball bearing, if $P_d/(2\delta)$ is greater than approximately -0.96 , at least if the number of rolling elements is greater than or equal to 5, as can be seen from Fig. 8(a). Fig. 7(a) also shows this for $|P_d/(2\delta)| \leq 0.5$ as z function. This means that for this $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter range the most loaded ball bear a greater portion of the external radial load than the most loaded cylindrical roller. This information can be useful in the mechanical system design, since the use of a cylindrical roller bearing, applied to this parameter $P_d/(2\delta)$ range, can better distribute the external radial load on rolling elements, than a ball bearing. As mentioned earlier for P_1/P ratio, note que if $P_d/(2\delta)$ increases, the P/P_1 ratio values tend towards 1 and reach the value 1 sooner or later, depending on the number of rolling elements in the bearing and $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter never reaches or exceeds the value 1, regardless of the number of rolling elements in the bearing.

If $P_d/(2\delta)$ is less than approximately -0.96 , for $z \geq 5$, $P_d/(2\delta) < -0.5$, for $z = 3$, or $P_d/(2\delta) < -1$, for $z = 2$ or 4, the P/P_1 ratio values computed for the ball bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing. For these parameter ranges it seems to be more convenient to use a ball bearing than a roller bearing as it distributes the external load more evenly. For $z = 3$ and $P_d/(2\delta) \geq -0.5$, and $z = 2$ or 4 and $P_d/(2\delta) \geq -1$, $P/P_1 = 1$, i.e., as $P_d/(2\delta)$ increases from these values, all the external radial load is being transferred by the most loaded rolling element.

The P/P_1 ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball bearing, if $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ is greater than a value, which can be

between -29.5 up to -8.5 , depending on the number of rolling elements in the bearing, at least if the number of rolling elements is greater than or equal to 5, as can be seen from Figs. 7(d) and 8(d). Unlike what is observed for the P/P_1 ratio values as a $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter function, the P/P_1 ratio values as a $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter function vary little - it is almost a plateau, denoted more for ball bearings than roller bearings - for negative values of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter and for any number of rolling elements in the bearing. For a given $z \geq 5$, increasing the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter from zero causes the P/P_1 ratio values to decrease from the characteristic plateau for the given number of rolling elements, to the value 1. The P/P_1 ratio values tend towards 1 and reach the value 1 sooner or later, depending on the number of rolling elements in the bearing. The greater the numbers of rolling elements in the bearing, the later P/P_1 ratio values reach the value 1; and when the P/P_1 ratio reaches the value 1, it is reached for both ball and roller bearings with the same number of rolling elements, for a single $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ value. Unlike what is observed for the $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter, there is no theoretical limit for the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter.

If $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) < -1$ and $z = 3$, the P/P_1 ratio values computed for the ball bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing and in both cases, $P/P_1 < 1$. So, the maximum rolling element load is greater than the external radial load, which is being transferred by the three rolling elements. The most loaded roller transfers a greater portion of the external radial load than the most loaded ball. The radial clearance is negative in this range of the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter; therefore all rolling elements are under preload before the external radial load is applied. With the application of the external radial load, two rolling elements are released when $P_d/2 = -\delta_{\max}$, $\delta_{\max} > 0$. For $z = 2$ and 4 the $P/P_1 = 1$ for both bearings, and for all $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ range. The external radial load is transferred by a single rolling element, the most loaded rolling element.

Figures 9(a) to (d) show P/P_1 ratios 3D-plots for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20.

Fig. 9 – P/P_1 ratios. As z and $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) ball bearings, (b) cylindrical roller bearings. As z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) ball bearings, (d) cylindrical roller bearings

The P_1/P ratio as a function of $P_d/(2\delta)$ for some values of z , as shown in Fig. 5(b), is the Mitrović’s load distribution factor definition. Figure 8(b) shows the reciprocal of the Mitrović’s load distribution factor. The reader can compare Fig. 8(b) of this work with Fig. 3 of the Mitrović’s paper, where the reciprocal of the Mitrović’s load distribution factor was plotted for z ranging from 5 to 20, for $0 < P_d/(2\delta) < 0.5$. Equation (7) whose plots are shown in Fig. 5(a), for ball and roller bearings and some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions, represents the ratio between the maximum admissible rolling element load and static load rating [19].

There are two differences in the way of calculating the Mitrović’s load distribution factor if Eq. (7) from this paper *or* Eq. (3) from Mitrović’s paper [19] is used. Firstly, Mitrović’s method is only valid for positive radial clearance. Secondly, the denominator of Eq. (7) contains a sum of loads in the direction of the external radial load, P , involving *all* rolling elements of the bearing, but only the active rolling elements are considered, which are determined by checking whether $\cos\psi_j$ is different from zero and greater than $P_d/(2\delta)$. These two checks must be carried out, since there is a possibility that rolling elements are loaded and don’t participate in the transfer of the load. The denominator of Eq. (3) of Mitrović’s paper, as well as Eq. (7) of Lazović *et al.*’s paper, contains a sum of loads in the direction of the external radial load, F_R , involving “ n ” rolling elements of the bearing, which represents the number of *pairs* of active rolling elements symmetric to the load line. Mitrović’s paper also only considers the active rolling elements, which are determined by checking whether $\cos\psi_j$ is greater than $P_d/(2\delta)$. Thus, by multiplying the sum of the “ n ” loads by 2 and adding the load of the most loaded element, the external radial load, F_R , is obtained. Note that $2n + 1 = z_s$, the odd number of rolling elements, which transfers the external radial load, which in the both Mitrović’s and Lazović *et al.*’s papers was taken to be equal to the number of active rolling elements for a ball bearing with *zero* radial clearance, defined by $z_s = 2\text{INT}((z + 3)/4) - 1$. To make it clearer, the denominators of the two equations in the two papers cited count up to “ n ”, which is a function of z_s defined for a ball bearing with *zero* radial clearance. Since the number “ n ” of pairs of active rolling elements, for a positive radial clearance, is always *less than* or *equal* to the number of pairs of active rolling elements for zero radial clearance, the count includes all active elements, and there is no difference in the Mitrović’s load distribution factor computation if Eq. (7) of this paper, Eq. (3) of Mitrović’s paper [19] or Eq. (7) of Lazović *et al.*’s paper [20] is used. However, if the radial clearance is negative, a count must be made up to the total

number z of rolling elements, with the elimination of rolling elements, which don't participate in the load transfer, since the number of pairs of active rolling elements, for a negative radial clearance, is always greater than or equal to the number of pairs of active rolling elements for zero radial clearance.

Even knowing that there is no difference in the calculation if the radial clearance is positive, and that the Mitrović's model does not apply to negative radial clearance, I still present some figures comparing the performance of Mitrović's model with respect to the model developed in this work.

The Figures 10(a) and (b) show a relative error in percentage, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ function, and Figs. 10(c) and (d), as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ function, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, respectively. From now on, *relative error* will be understood as being the absolute value of the difference between the load distribution factor, calculated by Eq. (3) from Mitrović's paper or Eq. (13) from Lazović *et al.*'s paper, for $i = 0$, or the reciprocals, with $n = 3/2$ for ball bearings and $n = 10/9$ for cylindrical roller bearings, and the computation using Eq. (7) from this work, or the reciprocal, divided by the load distribution factor, calculated by Eq. (7), or the reciprocal. Figure 10 show the relative errors of the reciprocals of load distribution factors of the mentioned equations, i.e., P/P_1 ratios.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 10 – Relative Errors of P/P_1 ratios when computed using the reciprocal of Eq. (3) from Mitrović's [19], with respect the computation using the reciprocal of Eq. (7) from this paper, for some z values. As $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) ball bearings, (b) cylindrical roller bearings. As $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) ball bearings, (d) cylindrical roller bearings

Examining Fig. 10 shows what was already expected. When $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameters decrease from a certain value, there is an increase in the relative error. If $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameters grow, the error decreases until, from a certain value, the relative error tends to a value close to zero.

Table 3 shows the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, below which the relative error, for some z values, increases, from about zero, with the decrease of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, for z varying from 2 to 20, and for ball or cylindrical roller bearings.

Tab. 3 - $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, below which the relative error in percentage, increases, from about zero, with the decrease of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$

z	$P_d/(2\delta)$	$P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$	z	$P_d/(2\delta)$	$P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$
2	-1	-	12	-0.5	0
3	-0.5	-1	13	-0.3546	
4	-1	-	14	-0.22252	
5	-0.80901	0	15	-0.10452	
6	-0.5		16	-0.38268	
7	-0.22252		17	-0.27366	
8	-0.7071		18	-0.17364	
9	-0.5		19	-0.08257	
10	-0.30901		20	-0.30901	
11	-0.14231				

3.3. Active rolling elements

For the configuration shown in Fig. 1, where the line of the external radial load passes through the most loaded rolling element's center, the rolling elements' number that effectively work on transferring the external load, n_{eff} , at least with regard to the parameter's range $|P_d/(2\delta)| < 1.0$, for $2 \leq z \leq 20$, is always odd, as shown in Fig. 11. For $P_d/(2\delta) < -1.0$ the only rolling elements, which don't transfer the external radial load between rings are those found at $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$. At these azimuth angular positions the rolling element/race normal contact line is perpendicular to the direction of external radial load. For $P_d/(2\delta) \geq 1.0$ all rolling elements are unloaded. In order to know if a rolling element participates in the load transfer and, therefore, if it's a valid term in the quasi-static equilibrium equation in the denominator of Eq. (7), a check is made if $\cos\psi_j$ is different from zero and greater than $P_d/(2\delta)$. If it's true, the term is computed to static balance and the sum of the elements, which effectively participate in the transfer, is incremented; otherwise, nothing is computed to static balance and added to the sum.

Fig. 11 - Rolling elements' number that effectively work on transferring the external radial load, n_{eff} , for some values of $P_d/(2\delta)$, as z 's functions – left to right and top to

bottom graphics are for the following $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: < -1 , -0.75 , -0.5 , -0.25 , 0 , 0.25 , 0.5 , 0.75 , ≥ 1 , and total

Figure 12 shows the number of rolling elements that effectively work in transferring the external radial load, n_{eff} , for some values of the $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$ parameter: -73 , -2.5 , 0 , 2.5 and 20 , for $2 \leq z \leq 20$. n_{eff} is always odd. If the number of rolling elements in the bearing is even, the rolling element located at $\psi = 180^\circ$ will never be loaded regardless of the value of $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$ parameter. The rolling elements located at $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$ never transfer the external radial load. If the bearing has a number of rolling elements that is multiple of four, then it has rolling elements located at $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$, and there are always three rolling elements, which don't transfer the load. For a bearing of up to twenty rolling elements, and for $P_d/(2\delta_{max}) \geq 20$, only the most loaded rolling element transfers the load. To obtain the plots in Fig. 12, the same procedure described in obtaining the plots in Fig. 11 was used.

Fig. 12 - Rolling elements' number that effectively work on transferring the external radial load, n_{eff} , for some values of $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$, as z 's functions – left to right and top to bottom graphics are for $P_d/(2\delta_{max}) = -73, -2.5, 0, 2.5, 20$, and total

Equation (7) can be multiplied by z to obtain

$$\frac{zP_1}{P} = \frac{z \left(1 - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n}{\sum_{j=1}^z \left(\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_j} = \frac{z \left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{max}} - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{max}}\right)^n}{\sum_{j=1}^z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{max}}\right) \cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_j}, \quad (8)$$

which represents the ratio between the maximum rolling element's load, P_1 , and the average radial external load, P/z . This ratio is defined as the Stribeck's Coefficient, S_s , for ball and roller bearings and differs from Stribeck's Constants or Numbers, which are approximations for Stribeck's Coefficients for z tending to infinity and for a rolling element bearing with zero radial clearance [3, 15].

3.4. zP_1/P ratios plots

Figures 13(a) to (f) show zP_1/P ratios plots, i.e., plots of Eq. (8), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$ values, as z 's functions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 13 – zP_1/P ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); for some $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f) - values adopted by Stribeck [1] for 10, 15 and 20 balls, circled by the red ellipses in Fig. 2, also are shown

Note that the values of the radial load ratios shown in Fig. 13 tend to stabilize with increasing number of rolling elements in the bearing. It's possible to see clearly that, with increasing z , the zP_1/P ratio tend to certain values, which are close to 4.37 for ball bearings and 4.08 for roller bearings, for zero radial clearance, which are the Stribeck's Numbers initially introduced by Stribeck and Palmgren, as shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 – Ratio between maximum rolling element’s load P_1 , assuming the maximum hertzian contact deflection as being equal to the relative displacement between the rings, and average radial external load, P/z , for zero radial clearance; and Stribeck’s Constants relative errors, as z ’s functions

Figure 14 shows a detail of Figs. 13(a) or (d), for $P_d/(2\delta) = P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 0$, and also shows plots of the Stribeck’s Constants’ error values as compared to the Stribeck’s Coefficients obtained numerically. The right-hand ordinate gives the relative Stribeck’s Constants’ error values [3]. Note that in the $10 \leq z \leq 20$ range, the ratio between the maximum ball load and the average external radial load can be approximated by the Stribeck’s Constant, 4.37, with a very small error - less than 0.14% - with respect to the values obtained numerically. The ratio between the maximum cylindrical roller load and the average external radial load can be approximated by the Stribeck’s Constant, 4.08, with a very small error - less than 0.33% - with respect to the values obtained numerically.

Figures 15(a) to (f) show zP_1/P ratios plots, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions.

(a)

Maximum Ball Load/Average Radial External Load

(b)

Maximum Cylindrical Roller Load/Average Radial External Load

(c)

Maximum Rolling Element Load/Average Radial External Load

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 15 – zP_1/P ratios. For ball and roller bearings and some z values as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) to (c); as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (d) to (f)

According to Figs. 15(a) and (d), given two bearings, a ball bearing and a cylindrical roller bearing, with the same number of rolling elements, the zP_1/P ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller (ball) bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball (cylindrical roller) bearing if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the second (fourth) columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The zP_1/P ratio values computed for both ball and roller bearings are equal and is worth z , which means that only the most loaded rolling element transfers the external radial load, if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the sixth columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Note that Figs. 15(a) and (d) are obtained from Figs. 5(a) and (d), respectively, by multiplying the P_1/P curves by the corresponding z values of rolling elements. Details of Figs. 15(a) and (d) are shown in Fig. 16, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, where it's possible to see clearly, for $P_d/(2\delta) = P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 0$, that, with increasing z , the zP_1/P ratio values tends to a certain value close to 4.37 for ball bearings and 4.08 for

cylindrical roller bearings. These values are the Stribeck's Constants or Numbers for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, respectively. The Fig. 16 shows that the difference between the Stribeck's Constants and the Stribeck's Coefficients obtained numerically, for a bearing with 20 rolling elements, is 8.17×10^{-4} for a ball bearing and 4.55×10^{-3} for a cylindrical roller bearing.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 16 – zP_1/P ratios for (a) ball and (b) cylindrical roller bearings and for some z values as $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions (detail)

Once the Stribeck's Constants' error values as compared to the Stribeck's Coefficients obtained numerically, decreases with z , for a bearing with 20 balls, the relative error is already very small, approximately 0.019%. The relative error for a bearing with 20 cylindrical rollers is also small, but it's about 6 times the relative error for bearings with 20 balls, i.e., approximately 0.11% (see Fig. 14).

Figures 17(a) to (b) show the 3D-plots of zP_1/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20.

Fig. 17 – zP_1/P ratios. As z and $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) ball bearings, (b) cylindrical roller bearings. As z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) ball bearings, (d) cylindrical roller bearings

3.5. $P/(zP_1)$ ratios plots

Figures 18(a) to (f) show $P/(zP_1)$ ratios plots, i.e., plots of the reciprocal of Eq. (8), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, as z 's functions.

(a)

Fig. 18 – $P/(zP_1)$ ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); for some $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f) - values adopted by Stribeck [1] for 10, 15 and 20 balls, circled by the red ellipses in Fig. 2, also are shown. For ball and roller

Figures 19(a) to (f) show $P/(zP_1)$ ratios plots, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions.

Fig. 19 – $P/(zP_1)$ ratios. For ball and roller bearings and some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) to (c); as $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (d) to (f)

Accordinging Figs. 19(a) and (d), given two bearings, a ball bearing and a cylindrical roller bearing, with the same number of rolling elements, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the ball (cylindrical roller) bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller (ball) bearing if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the second (fourth) columns of Table 1 and 2, respectively. The $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for both ball and cylindrical roller bearings are equal and is worth z^{-1} , which means that only the most loaded rolling element transfers the external radial load, if the $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter ranges are given, as z functions, in the sixth columns of Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Note that Figs. 19(a) and (d) can be obtained from Figs. 8(a) and (d), respectively, by dividing the P/P_1 curves by the corresponding rolling elements z values.

Given two bearings, a ball bearing and a cylindrical roller bearing, with the same number of rolling elements, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the ball bearing are greater than the values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing, if $P_d/(2\delta)$ is less than *approximately* -0.95 . Note that increasing the $P_d/(2\delta)$ value from this approximate value, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing start to become greater than the values computed for the ball bearing. The same occurs if $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ increases from -8.496 . For $P_d/(2\delta) = -0.89$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -8.4$, for example, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the ball bearing are greater than the values computed for the roller bearing, if $z = 3$. The $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values calculated for the two bearings are the same, if $z = 2$ and $z = 4$, and are worth $1/2$ and $1/4$, respectively. The $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing are greater than the values computed for the ball bearing, if $z > 4$, as shown in Figs. 19(a) and (d).

We know that $P_d/(2\delta) = 1$ is an superior boundary value for the $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter, since from then on, the total relative displacement between the rings is less than the radial clearance and all the rolling elements are unloaded. If the $P_d/(2\delta)$ ratio tends to 1 on the left, it's observed that the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the two bearings become the same for some value of $P_d/(2\delta)$, closer to 1 the greater the number of rolling elements in the bearing. This situation occurs when only one rolling element is loaded. For example, note that increasing the value of the parameter, when $P_d/(2\delta)$ reaches the value 0.5, for this value and above, for $z = 6$, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the two bearings become the same and equal to $1/6$, as shown in Figs. 19(a) to (c). Increasing the $P_d/(2\delta)$ parameter value even further, when $P_d/(2\delta) = 0.707$, for example, it's observed that, for this value and above, for $z = 8$, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing become equal to the values computed for the ball bearing and equal to $1/8$, and are greater for greater z values. The Fig. 20 shows that for $P_d/(2\delta) = 0.75$ ratio value, according to Fig. 11, up to $z = 8$ only one element is being loaded.

Fig. 20 – $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values for $P_d/(2\delta) = 0.75$, as z 's function

There is no upper limit for the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter. Note that, if $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ increases, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values calculated for the two bearings become the same for *some* value of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ and above, which increases if the number of rolling elements in the bearing increases. This situation occurs when only one rolling element is loaded. For example, increasing the parameter value, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ reaches the value 1, for this value and above, for $z = 6$, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the two bearings become the same and equal to $1/6$, as shown in Figs. 19(d) to (f). Increasing the $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter value even further, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 2.4143$, for example, for this value and above, for $z = 8$, the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing become equal to the values computed for the ball bearing and equal to $1/8$, and the $P/(zP_1)$ ratio values computed for the cylindrical roller bearing are greater to the values computed for the ball bearing for greater z values. The Figs. 18(d) to (f) show that for $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 2.5$ ratio value, up to $z = 8$ only one element is being loaded.

Figures 21(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of $P/(zP_1)$ ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20.

Fig. 21 – $P/(zP_1)$ ratios. As z and $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) ball bearings, (b) cylindrical roller bearings. As z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions: (c) ball bearings, (d) cylindrical roller bearings

4. RATIOS BETWEEN THE j^{th} ROLLING ELEMENT'S LOAD AND THE RADIAL EXTERNAL LOAD

From Eqs. (3) and (6), yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= k_n \delta^n \left(1 - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n = P_j \left(\frac{1 - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}}{\cos \psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}} \right)^n \\
 &= k_n \delta_{\max}^n \left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}} - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)^n = P_j \left[\frac{1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}} - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}}{\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right) \cos \psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}} \right]^n, \quad j = 1, \dots, z, \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

which substituted in Eq. (8), yields

$$\frac{zP_j}{P} = \frac{z \left(\cos \psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta} \right)^n}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left(\cos \psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta} \right)^n \cos \psi_k} = \frac{z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right) \cos \psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}} \right]^n}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right) \cos \psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}} \right]^n \cos \psi_k}. \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) represents the ratio between the j^{th} rolling element radial load and the average radial external load, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings.

Figure 22 is taken from Palmgren [2], who stated that experimental research, subsequent to Stribeck's paper, confirmed the results of Stribeck's Constants for zero and standard clearances, 4.37 and 5, respectively; and he showed experimental results for the load distribution on the balls, measured in a self-aligning ball bearing No. 1309, having a radial internal clearance of 0.01 mm, a clearance of 0.05 mm between the outer ring and the bearing housing under an external radial load of 675 kg. Such a distribution is shown by the solid line in Fig. 22(a), where the ordinate is in the unit zQ_{\max}/F_r , so it is directly comparable with the formulas for the Stribeck's Coefficients, zP_1/P . Here, there is a small spelling error, as the unit should be zQ_j/F_r , since, as it's written the result is a

constant and would not vary with the abscissa. The abscissa ψ represents the angle between the annular location of the ball in question and the direction of external radial load (Fig. 22(b)). Also, according to Palmgren, the dotted line in Fig. 22(a) provides, by way of comparison, the calculated load distribution for the ideal case of zero internal clearance and rigid rings.

Fig. 22 - (a) Palmgren's experimental results for the load distribution in a ball bearing, in the unit of Stribeck's Constant, as a function of azimuth angle. *Solid line* is for actual case with a clearance. *Dotted line* is for ideal case of zero internal clearance and rigid rings; (b) Azimuth angle for a bearing's rolling element

Source: Palmgren [2], p. 54

4.1. zP_j/P ratios plots

Figure 23 shows plots of Eq. (11), for $n = 3/2$ and $n = 10/9$, some values of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$, and z equal to 10, 15 and 20; which are plots of the ratios between the radial loads, P_j , and the average external radial load, P/z , versus the azimuth angle. These z values were chosen because they are in the z range between 10 and 20, a range whose ratio between the maximum rolling element load and the average external radial load, for ideal case of zero internal clearance, can be approximated, for ball (cylindrical roller) bearings, by the Stribeck's Constant, 4.37 (4.08), with a very small error - less than 0.14% (0.33%) - in relation to the values obtained numerically (see Fig. 14). The ratios between rolling element loads, which contribute to radial load transfer, and the average radial external load are indicated by small circles in Fig. 23. Polynomial interpolations are used to obtain continuous lines for both ball and cylindrical roller bearings, related to each pair of $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$ and z values. Dotted lines are used to interpolate experimental ball values taken from Fig. 22(a), for actual case with a clearance and for ideal case of zero radial internal clearance. For each value of $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{max})$, the three polynomial continuous lines associated with each z value, are so close to each other that it's impossible to distinguish them visually. However, the disparity between the three curves, for each z equal to 10, 15 and 20, increases with the relative radial clearance increase. The three continuous lines related to $P_d/(2\delta) = 0$ and z values equal to 10, 15 and 20; and one dashed line related to experimental values for $P_d = 0$, are very close, indicating a small error, one with respect to the other, and *all* lines approximate very well the ratios between the ball loads and the average radial load. It has been shown that adopting $P_d/(2\delta) \approx 0.34$, $P_d/(2\delta_{max}) \approx 0.5$ and z values equal to 10, 15 and 20, can satisfactorily reproduce the dashed line representing the experimental

values measured by Palmgren [2], for the actual case with a clearance, by polynomial interpolation.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 23 - zP_j/P ratios versus the azimuth angle for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, z equal to 10, 15 and 20; and experimental values for ball - taken from Fig. 22(a) - for actual case with a clearance and for ideal case of zero internal clearance. For some values of $P_d/(2\delta)$: (a) and (b), and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$: (c) and (d)

4.2. $P/(zP_j)$ ratios plots

Figure 24 shows plots of reciprocal of Eq. (11), for $n = 3/2$ and $n = 10/9$, some values of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, and z equal to 10, 15 and 20; which are plots of the ratios between the average external radial load, P/z , and the radial rolling element loads, P_j , versus the azimuth angle. Here in the plots representing the reciprocal expressions, it is confirmed that adopting $P_d/(2\delta) \approx 0.34$, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) \approx 0.5$ and z values equal to 10, 15 and 20, to obtain interpolating polynomials can satisfactorily reproduce the dashed line representing the experimental ball values measured by Palmgren [2].

Fig. 24 – $P/(zP_j)$ ratios versus the azimuth angle for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, z equal to 10, 15 and 20; and experimental values for ball - taken from Fig. 22(a) - for actual case with a clearance and for ideal case of zero internal clearance. For some values of $P_d/(2\delta)$: (a) and (b), and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$: (c) and (d)

Another relationship between the j^{th} rolling element load and the radial external load can be derived dividing Eq. (11) by z , yielding

$$\frac{P_j}{P} = \frac{\left(\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_j}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left(\cos\psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_k} = \frac{\left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_j}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)\cos\psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_k}. \quad (12)$$

Finally, the ratio between the j^{th} rolling element's load component in the direction of the radial external load, and the external radial load can be given by

$$\frac{P_j \cos\psi_j}{P} = \frac{\left(\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_j}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left(\cos\psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta}\right)^n \cos\psi_k} = \frac{\left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)\cos\psi_j - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_j}{\sum_{k=1}^z \left[\left(1 + \frac{|P_d|}{2\delta_{\max}}\right)\cos\psi_k - \frac{P_d}{2\delta_{\max}}\right]^n \cos\psi_k}, \quad (13)$$

which also are written as functions of the j^{th} rolling element's azimuth angular position, the relative radial clearance parameter with respect to the total relative displacement between rings, δ , or the relative radial clearance parameter with respect to additional elastic interference or compression at the load line, δ_{\max} .

The ratio between the load component of the j^{th} rolling element in the direction of the external radial load, $P_j \cos\psi_j$, and the external radial load, P , given by Eq. (13), for $n = 3/2$, as a function of total relative displacement between rings, δ_{\max} , is the definition of the Lazović *et al.*'s load distribution factor [20]. Likewise, Eq. (12) represents the definition of the *reduced* load distribution factor, which is the ratio between the normal rolling element's load, P_j , and the radial external load, P . However, as was stated for the P_j/P ratio, Eqs. (12) and (13), with δ given by Eq. (4) and P_d positive, negative or zero, yields a more generic result than the Lazović *et al.*'s results, since here I assume that P_j/P and $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ aren't only radial clearance functions, but also radial clearance's *sign* function. Furthermore, here the load distribution factor is defined not only for ball bearings, but also for cylindrical roller bearings. Besides, as well as Mitrović's model, the Lazović *et al.*'s load distribution factor model isn't appropriate for negative radial clearance.

4.3. P_j/P ratios plots

Figures 25(a) to (f) show P_j/P ratios plots, i.e., plots of the ratio between the j^{th} rolling element normal load, P_j , and the external radial load, P , given by Eq. (12), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, respectively, as z 's functions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 25 - P_j/P ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c) and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f)

Note that, for a given value of the $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameter, according to Figure 25, the participation of the most loaded rolling element in transferring the external radial load decreases with the increase of rolling elements in the bearing. As the 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements enter the load region, the P_j/P ratio for these rolling elements increases, passes through a maximum and drops again as the 3rd and $z^{\text{th}} - 1$ rolling elements enter the load region, and so on. To better illustrate the P_j/P ratios behavior as functions of the number of rolling elements in the bearing, some active rolling elements are shown separately. Figures 26 and 27 show P_j/P ratios details for $j = 1, 2, 3, z - 1$ and z and for $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ parameters ranging from -0.5 to 0.5, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 26 - P_j/P ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values and 1st, 2nd, 3rd, z^{th} and $z^{\text{th}} - 1$ rolling elements, according Fig. 1

(a)

(f)

Fig. 27 - P_j/P ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values and 1st, 2nd, 3rd, $z^{\text{th}} - 1$ and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1

Figures 26(a), (b) and 27(a), (b) show, for the ratio P_1/P , a *monotonic decrease* with increasing z and a *monotonic increase* with increasing $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ - see Fig. 6. Figures 26(c) to (f) and 27(c) to (f) show that, for low values of z , P_j/P , with $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z , increases with increasing z and decreases with increase in $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. For high values of z , P_j/P , with $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z , decreases with increasing z and increases with increasing $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. The arrows shown in Figs. 26 and 27 indicate the directions of growth and decrease of the P_j/P ratio, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ or $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ varies from the lowest - -0.5 - to the highest - $+0.5$ - values considered.

Figures 28(a) to (f) show the ratio between the j^{th} rolling element normal load, P_j , and the external radial load, P , given by Eq. (12), for ball and cylindrical rollers bearings, for some z values ranging from five to eight and for 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1; as relative radial clearance functions, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1.5 to $+1$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, which ranges from -10 to $+2.5$, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 28 - P_j/P ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings, some z values ranging from five up to eight, and for 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ functions: (a) to (c) and as $P_d/(2\delta_{\text{max}})$ functions: (d) to (f)

Figures 29(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of the reduced load distribution factor P_j/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z .

Fig. 29 – P_j/P ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta)$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

Figures 30(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of P_j/P ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z .

Fig. 30 – P_j/P ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

4.4. P/P_j ratios plots

Figures 31(a) to (f) show P/P_j ratios plots, i.e., plots of the reciprocal of Eq. (12), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values, as z 's functions.

(a)

Fig. 31 – P/P_j ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f)

Figures 32(a) to (f) show P/P_j ratios plots, the plots of the reciprocal of Eq. (12), for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for some z values, as $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ functions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 32 – P/P_j ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings and some z values as function of $P_d/(2\delta)$: (a) to (c) and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$: (d) to (f)

Figures 33(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of P/P_j ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z . The figures were truncated at $P/P_j = 10$ for better visualization.

Fig. 33 – P/P_j ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta)$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

Figures 34(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of P/P_j ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z . The figures were truncated at $P/P_j = 10$ for better visualization.

Fig. 34 – P/P_j ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

4.5. $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios plots

Figures 35(a) to (f) show the ratio between the load component of the j^{th} rolling element in the direction of the external radial load, $P_j \cos \psi_j$, and the external radial load, P , given by Eq. (13), for ball and cylindrical rollers bearings, as a function of z , for some values $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$.

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 35 – $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f)

Figures 36(a) and (j) show the $P_j \cos \psi_j / P$ ratios for some z values ranging from five to eight and for the 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1, as relative radial clearance functions, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1.5 to $+1$, and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 36 – $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios: Plots of the ratios between the j^{th} rolling element component load in the direction of the external radial load, $P_j \cos \psi_j$, and the external radial load, P , for z values ranging from five up to eight, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1, as relative radial clearance functions: (a) to (c) $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1.5 to $+1$; (d) to (f) $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$

The dashed vertical lines shown in the Figures above indicate the relative radial clearance value at which there is a change in the active rolling elements number. As shown in Fig. 36(a) to (c), more explicitly in Fig. 36(b), as the relative radial clearance with respect the ring's relative displacement increases, the Active Rolling Elements – ARE's – number for any z decreases. For $z = 5$, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(4\pi/5)$ the ARE's number goes from 5 to 3 and goes from 3 to 1 when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(2\pi/5)$. For $z = 6$, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(\pi)$ the ARE's number goes from 6 to 5, goes from 5 to 3 when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(2\pi/3)$ and when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(\pi/3)$ goes from 3 to 1. For $z = 7$, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(6\pi/7)$ the ARE's number goes from 7 to 5, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(4\pi/7)$ the number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(2\pi/7)$ goes from 3 to 1. For $z = 8$, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(\pi)$ the number goes from 6 to 5, when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(3\pi/4)$ the number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos(\pi/4)$ goes from 3 to 1.

In general, given a number z of rolling elements in the bearing, assuming that the variation in the relative radial clearance parameter must occur from the preload condition, where *all* rolling elements are loaded, the changes in the active rolling elements numbers, to the next lower odd number, must occur when $P_d/(2\delta) = \cos[(z - i)\pi/z]$, where, if z is odd i is also odd and given by $i = 1, 3, \dots, z - 2$, and if z is even i is also even and given by $i = 0, 2, \dots, (z-4)/2, (z+4)/2, \dots, z - 2$. In the latter case, odd values for i are ignored. If z is odd the changes occur from $z - (i - 1)$ to $z - (i + 1)$ ARE's. If $z = 4k, k = 1, 2, \dots$, the first change ($i = 0$) occurs from $z - 2$ to $z - 3$ ARE's. From the second, the changes occur from $z - (li - 1)$ to $z - (li + 1)$ ARE's, $l = 2, 3/2, 4/3, \dots$ for $i = 2, 4, \dots, (z-4)/2$, respectively; and from $z - (i - 1)$ to $z - (i + 1)$ ARE's, $i = (z+4)/2, \dots, z - 2$. If $z \neq 4k$ is even, the first change ($i = 0$) occurs from z to $z - 1$ ARE's. From the second, the changes occur from $z - (i - 1)$ to $z - (i + 1)$ ARE's, $i = 2, 4, \dots, z - 2$.

For $P_d/(2\delta) > \cos(\pi/4)$ – as also shown in the Fig. 11 for $P_d/(2\delta) = 0.75$ – for $z \leq 8$, only one rolling element is loaded. The Figs. 36(a) to (c), more specifically the Fig. 36(b), clearly demonstrates this for $5 \leq z \leq 8$; only the most loaded element is carrying the external radial load and, therefore, the load distribution factor for that element is 1 and for any other element is zero. Furthermore, for relative radial clearance values greater than or equal to 1, the radial clearance is greater than or equal to the relative radial displacement of the rings. In this case, no rolling element transfers load, as shown in Fig. 11, and load distribution factor does not apply.

The Fig. 36(e) confirms the results of Fig. 6 of Lazović's paper. Note that as the relative radial clearance with respect the maximum deflection increases, the number of Active Rolling Elements – ARE's – for any z decreases. For $z = 5$, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -4.236067977499792$ (not shown) the ARE's number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 0.447213595499958$ the ARE's number goes from 3 to 1. For $z = 6$, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -1.0$ the ARE's number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 1.0$ goes from 3 to 1. For $z = 7$, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -9.097834679044610$ (not shown) the ARE's number goes from 7 to 5, when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -0.286208264215581$ the ARE's number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 1.655970555211362$ goes from 3 to 1. For $z = 8$,

when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = -\sqrt{2}/(2 - \sqrt{2})$ the number goes from 5 to 3 and when $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = \sqrt{2}/(2 - \sqrt{2})$ goes from 3 to 1. For even z , $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ was not found, which indicate the change in the ARE number going from $z(z-2)$ to $z-1(z-3)$. For $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) > \sqrt{2}/(2 - \sqrt{2}) -$ as also shown in the Fig. 12 for $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 2.5$ - for $z \leq 8$, only one rolling element is loaded. The Fig. 36(e) clearly demonstrates this for $5 \leq z \leq 8$; only the most loaded element is carrying the external radial load and, therefore, the load distribution factor for that element is 1 and for any other element is zero. If a greater number of rolling elements in the bearing is assumed, for example, $z = 20$, the value of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ needed for the ARE's number goes from 3 to 1, increases to $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 19.431729094530649$. Figure 12 shows that at $P_d/(2\delta_{\max}) = 20$, $z \leq 20$, only the most loaded element is supporting the external radial load.

Figures 37(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z-1$ and z . The 3D-plots of $P_1 \cos(\psi_1)/P$, as functions of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and z , are the same shown for P_1/P in the Figs. 6(a) and (b).

Fig. 37 – $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta)$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

Figures 38(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z-1$ and z . The 3D-plots of $P_1 \cos(\psi_1)/P$ as functions of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ and z , are the same shown for P_1/P in the Figs. 6(c) and (d).

Fig. 38 – $P_j \cos(\psi_j)/P$ ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

4.6. $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios plots

Figures 39(a) to (f) show the ratio between the external radial load, P , and the load component of the j^{th} rolling element in the direction of the external radial load, $P_j \cos \psi_j$, given by the reciprocal of the Eq. (13), for ball and cylindrical rollers bearings, as a function of z , for some values $P_d/(2\delta)$ and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 39 – $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios. For ball and cylindrical roller bearings as z 's functions, for some $P_d/(2\delta)$ values: (a) to (c); and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ values: (d) to (f)

Figures 40(a) to (f) show the $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios for some z values ranging from five to eight and for the 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1, as relative radial clearance functions, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1.5 to $+1$, and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, respectively.

Fig. 40 – $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios: Plots of the ratios between the external radial load, P , and the j^{th} rolling element component load in the direction of the external radial load, $P_j \cos \psi_j$, for z values ranging from five up to eight, for ball and cylindrical roller bearings, and for 1st, 2nd and z^{th} rolling elements, according Fig. 1, as relative radial clearance functions: (a) to (c) $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1.5 to $+1$; (d) to (f) $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$

Figures 41(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta)$, ranging from -1 to $+1$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z . The 3D-plots of $P/(P_1 \cos \psi_1)$, as functions of $P_d/(2\delta)$ and z , are the same shown for P/P_1 in the Figs. 9(a) and (b). The figures are shown to $0 < P/(P_j \cos \psi_j) < 10$ for better visualization.

Fig. 41 – $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta)$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

Figures 42(a) to (d) show the 3D-plots of $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios for ball and cylindrical roller bearings as functions of relative radial clearance, $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$, ranging from -2.5 to $+2.5$, and z ranging from 2 to 20, for $j = 2, 3, z - 1$ and z . The 3D-plots of $P/(P_1 \cos \psi_1)$ as functions of $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$ and z , are the same shown for P/P_1 in the Figs. 9(c) and (d). The figures are shown to $0 < P/(P_j \cos \psi_j) < 10$ for better visualization.

Fig. 42 – $P/(P_j \cos \psi_j)$ ratios as functions of z and $P_d/(2\delta_{\max})$. Ball bearings: (a) $j = 2 = z$, (c) $j = 3 = z - 1$; cylindrical roller bearings: (b) $j = 2 = z$, (d) $j = 3 = z - 1$

5. CONCLUSIONS

A complete study of the influence of radial clearance on external radial load distribution in ball and cylindrical roller bearings has been made. It was assumed that the rings are rigid and that deformations are localized only in the small areas of contact between raceways and rolling elements. The Hertz model for localized elastic deformations was used. Plastic localized deformations are not considered. A simple model for the elastic deformations of rolling elements as a function of compression at the load line, azimuth angle, radial clearance and total relative displacement between the rings was introduced and explored, which takes into account positive, negative and zero radial clearance. Negative radial clearance (preload) has not been addressed in the literature since applications generally use small positive radial clearances to avoid heating and locking problems. However, current research has shown that a small preload is beneficial to bearing life. Results were shown in comparison with those in the literature for ratios between loads on the rolling elements and the external radial load. These ratios are referenced as load distribution factors.

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